

Analytical Model of the Internal Quantum Efficiency of Non-uniformly and Heavily Doped Silicon Solar Cells Including Non-ideal Effects

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Abstract— The Non-uniform doping profile is introduced in silicon solar cells particularly for achieving higher internal quantum efficiency and improved current-voltage characteristics. However, non-uniform and heavy doping levels introduce a number of non-ideal effects; the transport parameters (i.e. mobility and lifetime) become doping and field dependent, the space-dependency of the bandgap narrowing becomes significant and the Auger recombination mechanism becomes dominant. These effects adversely affect the internal quantum efficiency. Because of the evolving mathematical intractability, all these effects are not considered simultaneously in the existing models. This work resolves this intractability problem by using an elegant approximation technique called "Exponential Approximation Technique" and henceforth, develops an analytical model of the internal quantum efficiency for a drift-field Si-solar cell having non-uniform and heavy doping levels in the base region. The observed results of the proposed model shows that the drift-field solar cells have significantly higher internal quantum efficiency over the uniformly-doped Si-solar cells.

Index Terms—Internal quantum efficiency, drift-field solar cells, field dependency of mobility, non-uniformly doped base.

I. INTRODUCTION

Two most important concerns of a solar cell are the fill factor (FF) and the conversion efficiency. FF indicates how closely the current-voltage characteristic curve of a solar cell follows the rectangular shape formed by its short circuit current and open circuit voltage, whereas, the conversion efficiency measures the amount of electrical power produced from the incident solar radiation. Improved shape of the current-voltage characteristics increases both the FF and the conversion efficiency. Since the photo-generation current of a solar cell is opposed by its diode action, the current-voltage characteristics can be improved if the photo-generation current can be increased. One way to increase this photo-generation current is to develop electric fields in the bulk emitter and base regions in accordance with the built-in field developed in the depletion region. These fields can be developed by appropriate introduction of non-uniform and heavy doping levels in these bulk regions. The Drift-field (DF) solar cells are based on this concept [1]. Therefore, improved conversion efficiency is expected for the drift-field solar cells over the conventional solar cells.

Since increasing the peak doping levels in the bulk regions increases the strength of the developed fields therein, modern DF solar cells use increasingly heavy doping levels to increase the conversion efficiency. However, such heavy and non-uniform doping levels introduce a number of non-ideal effects which include doping dependence of the energy band-gap narrowing, the carrier mobility and the carrier lifetime, field dependence of the carrier mobility and dominance of the Auger recombination mechanisms. However, consideration of all these effects makes the modeling of the internal quantum efficiency analytically intractable. Therefore, the conventional models [2-5] found in the literature did not incorporate all these effects. Verhoff and Sinke [6] first considered almost all these non-ideal effects in their models; but, they considered the Auger recombination for the doping levels $\geq 5 \times 10^{18}$ and the SRH recombination for lower doping levels. Moreover, their models did not consider the field-dependency of the carrier mobility and are applicable for the dark saturation current, not for the internal quantum efficiency. Recently, Rashedul *et. al* [7] employed an elegant exponential approximation technique to resolve the mathematical intractability and developed an analytical model for the dark saturation current in the non-uniformly and heavily doped p-type base region considering both the SRH and the Auger recombination mechanisms simultaneously; but this model is not developed for the internal quantum efficiency. Therefore, this work is devoted to analytically model the internal quantum efficiency of the non-uniformly and heavily doped p-type base region of a drift-field solar cell by considering all of the above-mentioned non-ideal effects.

II. ANALYSIS

In order to derive the analytical model of the internal quantum efficiency of the heavily and non-uniformly-doped p-type base region of a Si-drift solar cell, the required equations are furnished as

$$J_n = qn(x)\mu_n(x)E(x) + qD_n(x)\frac{dn(x)}{dx} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{dJ_n}{dx} = q\left(\frac{n}{\tau_{ns}} + \frac{n}{\tau_{na}} - G\right) = \frac{qn}{\tau_{n,eff}} - qG \quad (2)$$

where μ_n and D_n are the electron mobility and the diffusivity, $E(x)$ is the electric field that acts on the electrons in the base region, τ_{ns} , τ_{na} , $\tau_{n,eff}$ are the SRH recombination lifetime, the Auger recombination lifetime and the effective carrier lifetime respectively and G is the generation rate.

The electric field $E(x)$ introduced in the base region is modified by the bandgap narrowing (BGN) effects owing to the heavy and non-uniform doping levels; therefore, $E(x)$ can be expressed as [8]

$$\frac{E}{V_T} = \frac{d}{dx} \ln N_a(x) - \frac{d}{dx} \ln n_{ie}^2(x) \quad (3)$$

where the effective intrinsic carrier concentration n_{ie} manifests itself due to BGN effects as [9]

$$n_{ie}^2(x) = n_{i0}^2 \left[\frac{N_a(x)}{N_{ref}} \right]^{\gamma_2} \quad (4)$$

with $n_{i0} = 1.194 \times 10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3}$, $N_{ref} = 1.3 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and $\gamma_2 = 0.5355$. For the doping density ranges used in the base region of the drift-field solar cells (of the order of $1 \times 10^{16} \text{ cm}^{-3} - 1 \times 10^{18} \text{ cm}^{-3}$), the electron mobility becomes doping dependent and can be expressed as [9]

$$\mu_{n0} = \frac{qD_n(0)}{kT} \left[\frac{N_a(x)}{N_{m,ref}} \right]^{-\gamma_1} \quad (5)$$

with $D_n(0) = 20.72 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ (V.s)}^{-1}$, $N_{m,ref} = 1 \times 10^{17} \text{ cm}^{-3}$

and $\gamma_1 = 0.42$. For heavily doped silicon, the doping dependent SRH and Auger recombination rates, under steady-state condition, are given by

$$R_{SRH} = \frac{n}{\tau_{ns}} = \frac{\tau_{n0}}{1 + \frac{N_a}{N_{0,ref}}} \quad [Ref.[10]] \quad (6)$$

$$R_{Auger} = \frac{n}{\tau_{na}} = \frac{1}{C_{Ap} N_a^2} \quad (7)$$

where τ_{ns} , τ_{na} are the carrier lifetime for the SRH and the Auger recombination respectively with $N_{0,ref} = 7.1 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ sec}$, $\tau_{n0} = 3.95 \times 10^{-4} \text{ sec}$ [11]

and $C_{Ap} = 0.72 \times 10^{-31} - 0.15 \times 10^{-34} T + 2.92 \times 10^{-37} T^2$ is the Auger coefficient for electrons [12]. The steady-state generation rate due to optical illumination G_n is given by

$$G(x) = \frac{q\alpha\lambda}{hc} I_0 e^{-\alpha(\lambda)x} = G_0 e^{-\alpha(\lambda)x} \quad (8)$$

where I_0 is the irradiance at the surface and α is the absorption coefficient of silicon at a given wavelength (λ).

Finally, the electron current continuity equation [Eqn. (2)] can be organized as

$$\frac{dJ_n}{dx} = \frac{qn}{\tau_{n,eff}} - G_0 e^{-\alpha x} \quad (9)$$

where $\tau_{n,eff}$ is the effective electron lifetime given by

$$\frac{1}{\tau_{n,eff}} = \frac{\tau_{n0}}{1 + \frac{N_a}{N_{0,ref}}} + C_{Ap} N_a^2 \quad (10)$$

A second order differential equation (DE) of $n(x)$ can be obtained by combining Eqn. (1) with Eqn. (9) as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2 n}{dx^2} + \left[\frac{E}{V_T} - \frac{d}{dx} \ln \left(\frac{1}{qD_n} \right) \right] \frac{dn}{dx} \\ + \left[\frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{E}{V_T} \right) - \frac{E}{V_T} \frac{d}{dx} \ln \left(\frac{1}{qD_n} \right) - \frac{1}{\tau_{n,eff} D_n} \right] n \\ = - \left[\frac{G_0 e^{-\alpha(W_e + W_a)}}{D_n} \right] e^{-\alpha x} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where W_e , W_a are the widths of the emitter and the absorber respectively. In this work the base doping profile is chosen as exponential and can be expressed as

$$N_a(x) = N_a(0) e^{\frac{\eta x}{W_b}} = N_a(0) u(x) \quad (12)$$

where '0' and ' W_b ' denote the depletion edge of the junction and the surface of the base, u is a suitable variable and

$\eta = \log \left[\frac{N_a(W_b)}{N_a(0)} \right]$ is the logarithmic slope of the doping

profile. Therefore, for this exponential profile, the electric field, the mobility and the lifetime of electrons in the base region can be furnished as

$$\frac{En}{V_T} = \frac{\eta}{W_b} (1 - \gamma_2) \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{1}{qD_n} = \frac{1}{qD_n(0)} \left[\frac{N_a(0)}{N_{0ref}} \right]^{\gamma_1} u^{\gamma_1} = F_e u^{\gamma_1} \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{1}{\tau_{ns}} = \frac{1}{\tau_{n0}} \left(1 + \frac{N_a(0)u}{N_{0ref}} \right) = R_{ns} \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{1}{\tau_{na}} = C_{Ap} [N_a(0)u]^2 = R_{na} \quad (16)$$

and the DE [Eqn. 12] can be organized as

$$\frac{d^2 n}{dx^2} + G_1 \frac{dn}{dx} + G_2 n = 0 \quad (17)$$

where $G_1 = \frac{\eta}{W_b} (1 - \gamma_2 - \gamma_1)$,

$$G_2 = - \left[\left(\frac{\eta}{W_b} \right)^2 \gamma_1 (1 - \gamma_2) + \frac{R_{ns} + R_{na}}{D_n} \right]$$

It is evident that the analytical intractability of the DE is because of the presence of the second term of G_2 , which not only incorporates both the SRH and the Auger recombination but also depends on the position-dependent doping profile. Verhoff and Sinke [6] separately considered the SRH and Auger recombination to resolve the intractability. In this work, however, using the exponential approximation technique [7], this term can be approximated to a simple exponential as

$$\frac{(R_{ns} + R_{na})}{D_n} = \frac{1}{\tau_{n,eff} D_n} \equiv \frac{1}{L_{n,eff}^2} u^{k_n} \quad (18)$$

The solution of the DE [Eqn. 18] gives $n(x)$ as a linear combination of modified Bessel functions of the first kind I_β and of the second kind K_β of order β [Appendix A]

$$n(x) = w(x) \{ C_1 + v_1 I_\beta(x) + (C_2 + v_2) K_\beta(x) \} \quad (19)$$

The wavelength dependent total photocurrent density is [13]

$$J_{ph}(\lambda) = J_p(W_e)(\lambda) + J_G(\lambda) + J_n(0)(\lambda) \quad (20)$$

where $J_p(W_e)$ and J_G are the photocurrent generated in the uniformly doped emitter and in the depletion region respectively [13] and $J_n(0)$ is the photo-generated current density obtained from the electron current equation given by (1) at the depletion edge i.e. $x = 0$. Finally, the wavelength dependent internal quantum efficiency can be obtained as

$$\eta_i(\lambda) = \frac{J_{ph}(\lambda)}{qG_0(\lambda)} \times 100\% \quad (21)$$

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section the results of internal quantum efficiency considering exponential doping profile in the base for a Si-drift solar cell are presented. The results of the 'present model' are compared against those of a Si-solar cell that employs uniform doping profile throughout the emitter and the base region ('previous model').

Figs. (1) to (3) show the internal quantum efficiency of the present model in comparison with that of the previous model. In all of these figures, it is evident that non-uniform base doping profile causes internal efficiency to increase for the low-energy photons. This is obvious, since non-uniformity of the base doping profile is such that it creates an electric field in the neutral base region in the same direction as the field in the depletion region. This field causes photo-generated carriers for low-energy photons in the base region to pass with an increased velocity, thereby, increases the photo-current.

Fig. (1) also shows that increase in the base width increases the internal quantum efficiency. This is due to the fact that increase in the base width increases the absorption of low-energy photons. Fig. (2) shows that the internal quantum

efficiency decreases with the increase of the surface recombination velocity at the base surface. Since surface recombination velocity causes carrier loss at the base surface, the more the surface recombination, the less will be the internal quantum efficiency. Again, increase in $N_a(0)$ i.e. the base doping level at the junction (at $x = 0$) keeping the peak doping level constant causes a reduction in the doping gradient in the base and hence, reduces the electric field. Therefore, the photo-generated carriers in the base experience a lowered-level of field causing the photo-current to decrease. This fact is observed in the Fig. (3).

Fig. 1: Internal quantum efficiency vs. photon energy for the present model and the previous model. Here, two base widths of 2 μm and 4 μm are considered, $S_n = 1 \times 10^5$ cm/sec, $N_a(0) = 1 \times 10^{16}$ cm^{-3} and $N_a(W_b) = 1 \times 10^{18}$ cm^{-3} .

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, an analytical investigation has been made to observe the effects of the non-uniform base doping profile on the internal quantum efficiency of a drift-field solar cell. The model includes the bandgap narrowing, the doping dependency of the carrier mobility and also, of the SRH and the Auger lifetime. The resulting intractability of the governing differential equation has been resolved by employing an exponential approximation technique. The simulation results obtained from the developed model reveal that the non-uniformity of the base doping causes the internal quantum efficiency to increase, particularly, for the low energy photons.

APPENDIX A

SOLUTION OF THE DE

Using $n(x) = v(x)w(x)$ leads the DE (17) to

$$\frac{d^2 v}{dx^2} + \left[\frac{2}{w} \frac{dw}{dx} + G_1 \right] \frac{dv}{dx} + \frac{1}{w} \left[\frac{d^2 w}{dx^2} + G_1 \frac{dw}{dx} + G_2 w \right] v = - \left[\frac{G_0 e^{-\alpha(W_e + W_a)}}{D_n} \right] \frac{e^{-\alpha x}}{w} = G_L \frac{e^{-\alpha x}}{w D_n} \quad (22)$$

Fig. 2: Internal quantum efficiency vs. photon energy for the present model and the previous model. Here, two surface recombination velocities of $S_n = 1 \times 10^5$ cm/sec and $S_n = 1 \times 10^6$ cm/sec are considered, $W_b = 2 \mu\text{m}$, $N_a(0) = 1 \times 10^{16}$ cm⁻³ and $N_a(W_b) = 1 \times 10^{18}$ cm⁻³.

Fig. 3: Internal quantum efficiency vs. photon energy for the present model and the previous model. Here, two base doping densities at $x = 0$ of 1×10^{17} cm⁻³ and 1×10^{18} cm⁻³ are considered, $S_n = 1 \times 10^5$, $W_b = 2 \mu\text{m}$ and $N_a(W_b) = 1 \times 10^{18}$ cm⁻³.

Letting $\frac{2}{w} \frac{dw}{dx} + G_1 = 0$ and $u^{k_n} = z^2$ lead $w(x)$ and $v(x)$ to

$$w(x) = e^{-\frac{1}{2} \int G_1(x) dx} = u^{-\frac{1-\gamma_2-\gamma_1}{2}} \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{d^2 v}{dX^2} + \frac{1}{X} \frac{dv}{dX} - \frac{1}{X^2} (X^2 + \beta^2) v = 0 \quad (24)$$

where $X = \frac{2W_B}{\eta k_n L_{n,eff}} z = b_0 z$. Finally, $n(x)$ can be given by

$$n(x) = g_0 w(x) \{ C_{20} - V_2 \} K_\beta(X) - (C_{10} - V_1) I_\beta(X) \quad (25)$$

where $g_0 = \left[\frac{2W_b}{\eta k_n} \right] q F_e \alpha G_L$, $\beta = \frac{1-\gamma_2+\gamma_1}{k_n}$,

$$V_1(x) = \int K_\beta z^\beta e^{-\alpha x} dx \text{ and } V_2(x) = \int I_\beta z^\beta e^{-\alpha x} dx.$$

The constants C_{10} , C_{20} can be determined from the boundary conditions $n(0) = 0$ and $J_n(W_b) = -q S_n n(W_b)$ [6], where S_n is the surface recombination velocity at the base surface.

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